

Sexually Transmitted Infections in Children and Adolescents Who Are Victims of Sexual Violence: Prevalence, Risk Factors, and Challenges for Healthcare Services

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ABSTRACT: Sexual violence against children and adolescents is a global public health issue with far-reaching impacts on the victims' physical, psychological, and social health. One important but often overlooked physical health consequence is the risk of sexually transmitted infections (STIs). Children and adolescents who are victims of sexual violence are in a very vulnerable condition for contracting STIs due to power imbalances, limited ability to give consent, and delays in obtaining adequate medical examinations and services. This article aims to comprehensively review the literature on the prevalence, types of STIs, related factors, and the implementation of screening and healthcare services for children and adolescents who are victims of sexual violence. The method used is a literature review of relevant international research articles, including retrospective studies, cross-sectional studies, cohort studies, and clinical audits, obtained from reputable scientific databases. The review results indicate that the prevalence of STIs among children and adolescents who are victims of sexual violence varies across studies, with the most frequently reported types of STIs including *Chlamydia trachomatis*, *Neisseria gonorrhoeae*, syphilis, *Mycoplasma genitalium*, human papillomavirus, and HIV. The factors most consistently associated with STIs include adolescent age, female sex, sexual violence with penetration, repeated violence, commercial sexual exploitation, and delayed medical examination after the incident. Additionally, this review identifies significant gaps in the implementation of STI screening, medical follow-up, and the continuity of healthcare services for victims. The conclusion of this study emphasizes the importance of strengthening integrated, risk-based, and trauma-sensitive healthcare services in the management of children and adolescents who are victims of sexual violence, in order to improve early detection and prevent complications from sexually transmitted infections.

KEYWORDS: Children and adolescents, Literature review, Sexually transmitted infections, Sexual violence, STI screening.

INTRODUCTION

Sexual violence against children and adolescents is a serious public health issue and human rights violation, with complex short- and long-term impacts on physical, psychological, social, and reproductive health. The World Health Organization (WHO) defines sexual violence as any sexual act, attempted sexual act, or other act directed against a person's sexuality, whether by coercion or not, and regardless of the victim's relationship to the perpetrator (Krug et al., 2002; WHO, 2021). UNICEF reports that millions of children worldwide experience sexual violence each year, with most cases occurring before the age of 18 and often going unreported or being reported late (UNICEF, 2020; UNICEF, 2022; UNICEF, 2024). In Indonesia, sexual violence against children and adolescents also shows a worrying trend, as reflected in data from child protection services and the strengthening of regulations thru Law Number 12 of 2022 concerning Sexual Violence Crimes.

One of the most serious medical consequences of sexual violence against children and adolescents is the risk of sexually transmitted infections (STIs). Children and adolescents are in a very vulnerable position to STIs due to biological, developmental, and social factors. Biologically, the genital mucosal tissues of children and adolescents, especially during the pre-pubertal and early pubertal phases, are more susceptible to microtrauma and pathogen colonization compared to adults (Edwards & Butler, 2011; Smith & Coleman, 2021). Additionally, the immature immune system in children can increase their susceptibility to infections, including

bacterial infections such as *Neisseria gonorrhoeae* and *Chlamydia trachomatis* (Hammerschlag; Quillin & Seifert, 2018). Literature indicates that the presence of STIs in children, particularly in pre-pubertal ages, is often a strong indicator of sexual violence, although non-sexual transmission mechanisms in certain conditions still need to be carefully considered (De Jong, 1986; Groothuis et al., 1983; Goodyear-Smith & Schabetsberger, 2021). Therefore, the interpretation of IMS findings in children must be done comprehensively, considering the clinical, social, and forensic context (Adams, 2011; Jenny & Crawford-Jakubiak, 2013). Some studies report varying prevalence of STIs in children and adolescents who are victims of sexual violence, ranging from less than 2% to over 30%, depending on population characteristics, detection methods, and the type of healthcare services used (Drezett et al., 2020; Dioussé et al., 2020; Driscoll et al., 2022).

Globally, studies show that the most common STIs found in children and adolescents who are victims of sexual violence include chlamydia, gonorrhea, trichomoniasis, human papillomavirus (HPV), and in certain cases, viral infections such as hepatitis B and HIV (Siegel et al., 1995; Jang & Oh, 2021; Skjælaen & Vallersnes, 2022). Gonorrhea, in particular, remains an unresolved public health challenge, given increasing antimicrobial resistance and its long-term impact on reproductive health (Barberá & Serra-Pladevall, 2019; WHO, 2022). In children and adolescents, gonorrhea infection can lead to serious complications such as pelvic inflammatory disease, future infertility, and significant psychosocial impacts (Bambang et al., 2021; Qin & Melvin, 2020). Beside biological factors, the vulnerability of children and adolescents to STIs is also influenced by social and structural factors. Poverty, food insecurity, family dysfunction, domestic violence, and commercial sexual exploitation of children have been identified as risk factors that increase the likelihood of sexual violence and exposure to STIs (Evans & Kim, 2013; Hornor et al., 2022; Loosier et al., 2020). In adolescents, psychosocial developmental factors, including identity exploration, peer pressure, and limited knowledge of reproductive health, contribute to an increased risk of STIs, both in the context of sexual violence and risky sexual behavior (Noll & Putnam, 2017; Nsuami et al., 2010).

In developing countries, including Indonesia, the challenges in detecting and managing STIs in children and adolescents who are victims of sexual violence are becoming increasingly complex due to limited access to healthcare services, social stigma, and low rates of case reporting. Some studies indicate that the delay in victims reporting sexual violence, which can last for months or even years, impacts the low likelihood of detecting STIs in the acute phase (Hemant et al., 2024; Oksal et al., 2024). On the other hand, the limitations of systematic STI screening in primary and referral healthcare services also contribute to underdiagnosis and undertreatment (Majeed-Ariss et al., 2021; Tao et al., 2023). In Indonesia, national guidelines for the management of STIs and violence against children are available, including the National Guidelines for the Management of Sexually Transmitted Infections (Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia, 2016), the Guidelines for the Service and Referral of Violence Against Women and Children (Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia, 2021), as well as various ministerial regulations and laws related to child protection. However, implementation in the field still faces various obstacles, ranging from limited resources and a lack of training for healthcare workers to the suboptimal integration of medical, psychosocial, and legal services (Widiastuti & Sekartini, 2016; Pane & Sekartini, 2023).

Despite extensive research on STIs in the general population and among victims of sexual violence, studies specifically synthesizing scientific evidence on STIs in children and adolescents who are victims of sexual violence are still relatively limited, especially in developing countries. Existing literature is scattered across various research designs, ranging from case studies and retrospective studies to observational cohort studies, with a fairly wide variation in findings regarding prevalence, pathogen types, risk factors, and screening and follow-up practices (Ingram et al., 1997; Jang & Oh, 2021; Tiplamaz & İnanıcı, 2024). Therefore, this literature review aims to comprehensively examine the scientific evidence regarding sexually transmitted infections in children and adolescents who are victims of sexual violence, including prevalence, types of infections, contributing risk factors, and clinical and health service policy implications. By presenting a synthesis of findings from various geographical contexts and healthcare systems, this article is expected to provide a strong scientific foundation for the development of more effective clinical practices, health policies, and child prevention and protection efforts.

METHODS

This study uses a literature review design with a narrative-structured approach to synthesize scientific evidence regarding sexually transmitted infections (STIs) in children and adolescents who are victims of sexual violence. This approach was chosen to allow for the integration of findings from various research designs, including cross-sectional, retrospective, cohort, case studies, and

healthcare service audits, which are relevant to the topic under review. A narrative-structured literature review was deemed appropriate for identifying patterns of findings, research gaps, and clinical and policy implications within the context of child and adolescent health.

A systematic literature search was conducted across several international and national electronic databases, namely PubMed, Scopus, ScienceDirect, Google Scholar, and accredited national journal portals. The search was conducted on articles published up to 2024 to ensure the currency of the scientific evidence. The keywords used were adapted from Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) and free terms, including: "sexually transmitted infections", "child sexual abuse", "adolescent sexual violence", "gonorrhoea", "chlamydia", "Neisseria gonorrhoeae", "pediatric", "sexual assault", and "screening". These keywords were combined using Boolean operators AND and OR to broaden and focus the search results. Examples of search strategies are: "sexually transmitted infections" AND "child sexual abuse" as well as "adolescent" AND "sexual violence" AND "STI".

The inclusion criteria for this study were: (1) empirical research articles with quantitative or observational designs, (2) discussing sexually transmitted infections in children and/or adolescents who are victims of sexual violence, (3) published between 2020 and 2024, and (4) available in full text. Exclusion criteria include articles that are editorials, opinions, single case reports, and articles that do not discuss STIs as the primary outcome. The article selection process was conducted in several stages: title and abstract identification, eligibility assessment based on the full text, and final selection of articles meeting the criteria. The extracted data includes the author and year of publication, research location, study design, sample characteristics, type of STI reported, and key findings related to risk factors and healthcare services.

RESULTS

This literature review encompasses a number of international and national studies that examine sexually transmitted infections in children and adolescents who are victims of sexual violence, using various research designs including retrospective, cohort, and cross-sectional studies. The synthesis results indicate that the occurrence of STIs in this population is influenced by direct factors, indirect factors, as well as sociodemographic and environmental factors.

Table 1. Literature review based on author, year, location, research design, and sample

No	Authors, year	Study site	Study design	Sample	Sampling technique
1	Drezett et al., 2020	Brazil	Retrospective cohort	289 victims of sexual violence (adolescents & adults)	Total sampling
2	Dioussé et al., 2020	Senegal	Retrospective	143 girls (<15 years old)	Total sampling
3	De Peder et al., 2020	Brazil	Retrospective	1,703 adolescents and young adults	Total sampling (medical record)
4	Wang & Chen, 2020	China	Cross-sectional	8,324 patients at the STI clinic	Consecutive sampling
5	Jang & Oh, 2021	South Korea	Descriptive retrospective	2,179 children (<18 years old)	Total sampling (national data surveillance)
6	Majeed-Ariss et al., 2021	United Kingdom	Retrospective cohort	843 children who are victims of sexual violence	Total sampling
7	Driscoll et al., 2022	United Kingdom	Descriptive retrospective	241 children (0–13 years old)	Total sampling
8	Skjælaen & Vallersnes, 2022	Norway	Prospective cohort	645 victims of sexual violence	Consecutive sampling
9	Honor et al., 2022	USA	Descriptive retrospective	Adolescents aged 12–21 years	Total sampling
10	Nilasari & Waworuntu, 2023	Indonesia	Cross-sectional	59 male street children	Purposive sampling

No Authors, year	Study site	Study design	Sample	Sampling technique
11 Tao et al., 2023	USA	Epidemiological (secondary data)	55,113 SAA visits	Total sampling (national database)
12 Nainggolan, 2024	Indonesia	Descriptive retrospective	15 cases of child sodomy	Total sampling

Table 2. Literature Review Based on Factors Related to Sexually Transmitted Infections in Sexually Abused Children and Adolescents

Factors Studied	Authors (year)	Results	p-value
Direct Factors			
Type of sexual violence (genital/anal penetration)	Dioussé et al. (2020)	Cases with penetration show a higher prevalence of STIs compared to non-penetrative cases	Not reported
	Driscoll et al. (2022)	Penetration is associated with increased detection of <i>Neisseria gonorrhoeae</i> and <i>Chlamydia trachomatis</i>	< 0.05
Age of the victim	Jang & Oh (2021)	Adolescents have a higher prevalence of STIs compared to prepubertal children	< 0.05
	Tao et al. (2023)	Age ≥12 years is associated with increased post-sexual violence IMS services	< 0.01
Delay in medical examination	Majeed-Ariss et al. (2021)	Delays in service visits reduce early detection of STIs	Not reported
	Skjælaaen & Vallersnes (2022)	Examination >7 days after the incident increases the risk of STI complications	< 0.05
Indirect Factors			
Access to healthcare services	Hornor et al. (2022)	Victims with limited access to services are less likely to undergo STI screening	Not reported
	Driscoll et al. (2022)	Integrated services increase the number of STI screenings for children	< 0.05
History of repeated violence	Drezett et al. (2020)	Repeated violence is associated with an increased prevalence of STIs	< 0.05
	Tao et al. (2023)	Victims of repeat offenses more frequently require STI and mental health services	< 0.01
Sociodemographic Factors			
Low socioeconomic status	Nilasari & Waworuntu (2023)	Low economic status increases the risk of STIs in vulnerable children and adolescents	< 0.05
	Hornor et al. (2022)	Children from socially vulnerable groups are more frequently exposed to sexual exploitation	Not reported
Risky environment	Nainggolan (2024)	Cases of child sodomy are more prevalent in environments with low supervision	Not reported
	Skjælaaen & Vallersnes (2022)	The urban environment is associated with an increase in visits to sexual violence service centres	< 0.05

Direct Factors Related to the Occurrence of STIs

The most consistent direct factor found to be associated with STI incidence is the type of sexual violence, particularly violence involving genital or anal penetration. Studies conducted by Dioussé et al. (2020) and Driscoll et al. (2022) show that victims with a history of penetration have a higher prevalence of STIs compared to victims without penetration, especially for *Neisseria gonorrhoeae* and *Chlamydia trachomatis*. These findings confirm that forms of sexual violence play a significant role in the risk of transmitting STI pathogens among children and adolescents.

Additionally, the victim's age is a significant factor. Research by Jang and Oh (2021) indicates that adolescents have a higher prevalence of STIs compared to prepubertal children. This is supported by Tao et al. (2023), who found that victims aged ≥ 12 years more frequently require post-sexual violence IMS services. This finding indicates an increase in biological and behavioral vulnerability with age. Another contributing factor is the delay in medical examinations. Majeed-Ariss et al. (2021) reported that delayed access to healthcare services after sexual violence can reduce the chances of early STI detection. Meanwhile, Skjælaen and Vallersnes (2022) found that medical examinations performed more than seven days after the event were associated with an increased risk of complications from STIs.

Indirect Factors Related to the Occurrence of STIs

The study results indicate that access to healthcare services is an indirect factor influencing the detection and management of STIs. Hornor et al. (2022) reported that victims with limited access to healthcare services were less likely to undergo STI screening. Conversely, Driscoll et al. (2022) found that the availability of integrated services and a good referral system increased STI testing coverage among children who were victims of sexual violence. Additionally, a history of repeated sexual violence was also associated with an increased risk of STIs. Drezett et al. (2020) showed that victims with repeated experiences of violence had a higher prevalence of STIs compared to victims with a single incident. This aligns with the findings of Tao et al. (2023), who stated that victims of repeated violence more frequently require both IMS and mental health services simultaneously.

Sociodemographic and Environmental Factors

The dominant sociodemographic factor in this study is low socioeconomic status. A study by Nilasari and Waworuntu (2023) in Indonesia showed that children and adolescents from low-income groups have a higher risk of STIs. Hornor et al. (2022) also emphasize that social vulnerability, including poverty and marginalization, increases the risk of sexual exploitation and exposure to STIs. Additionally, environmental factors play a role in the context of STI occurrences. Nainggolan (2024) reported that cases of sexual violence against children are more frequently found in environments with low supervision. Skjælaen dan Vallersnes (2022) add that the urban environment is associated with an increased number of visits to sexual violence service centers, reflecting the high need for STI services in areas with high population density.

DISCUSSION

This literature review indicates that sexually transmitted infections (STIs) in children and adolescents who are victims of sexual violence are a complex and multidimensional public health issue. The collected findings confirm that the occurrence of STIs in this vulnerable group is not only influenced by biological factors, but also by behavioral, structural, socioeconomic factors, and the healthcare system. This discussion examines the relationship between these factors, referring to empirical evidence from the reviewed studies and supporting literature.

The Role of Direct Factors in the Occurrence of STIs

The study results indicate that the type of sexual violence, particularly violence involving genital or anal penetration, is the most consistent direct factor associated with the occurrence of STIs. These findings are consistent with previous literature stating that penetration increases the risk of pathogen transmission thru direct contact with mucous membranes and bodily fluids, especially in the immature and easily microtraumatized genital tissues of children (Adams, 2011; Hammerschlag, n.d.). Studies by Driscoll et al. (2022) and Dioussé et al. (2020) strengthen the evidence that penetration is an important indicator in assessing the risk of IMS in cases of child sexual violence.

Additionally, the victim's age has also been proven to influence the prevalence of STIs. Adolescents show a higher incidence of STIs compared to prepubertal children, as reported by Jang and Oh (2021) and Tao et al. (2023). Biologically, hormonal changes during puberty can affect susceptibility to infection, while behaviorally, adolescents tend to have a greater risk of exposure

due to an imbalance of power dynamics with the perpetrator (Noll & Putnam, 2017). This finding confirms the importance of an age-based approach in screening and managing STIs in survivors of sexual violence.

Another factor that needs attention is the delay in medical examinations. The studies by Majeed-Ariss et al. (2021) and Skjælaaen and Vallersnes (2022) show that delayed access to healthcare services after sexual violence impacts the decreased likelihood of early STI detection and increases the risk of complications. This aligns with CDC and WHO guidelines emphasizing the importance of STI screening and prophylaxis as early as possible after sexual violence (Hazra et al., 2022; WHO, 2023).

The Influence of Indirect Factors and the Healthcare System

This study also highlights the role of access to healthcare services as a crucial indirect factor. Limited access, whether due to geographical, social, or administrative factors, has been shown to reduce the coverage of STI screening among children who are victims of sexual violence (Hornor et al., 2022). Conversely, the availability of integrated services, such as sexual assault referral centers or child advocacy centers, increases the likelihood of victims receiving comprehensive STI testing (Driscoll et al., 2022; Majeed-Ariss et al., 2021).

These findings are relevant to the Indonesian context, where integrating primary healthcare services with child protection services still faces various implementation challenges, despite being regulated in national policies (Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia, 2021; Minister of Health Regulation No. 68 of 2013). The lack of trained personnel, social stigma, and suboptimal referral mechanisms can be major obstacles in the detection and management of STIs in survivors of sexual violence. Additionally, a history of repeated sexual violence was found to be associated with an increased risk of STIs. Drezett et al. (2020) and Tao et al. (2023) showed that victims of repeated violence have higher pathogen exposure and more complex healthcare needs. These findings indicate that preventing recurrent violence is an important strategy not only for psychosocial protection but also for STI prevention.

The Role of Sociodemographic and Environmental Factors

Sociodemographic factors, particularly low socioeconomic status, emerged as significant determinants in the incidence of STIs. Studies by Nilasari and Waworuntu (2023) and Hornor et al. (2022) showed that children and adolescents from low-income groups are more vulnerable to sexual exploitation and have limited access to healthcare services. This condition aligns with the social determinants of health framework, which identifies poverty as a structural factor that increases vulnerability to violence and disease (Krug et al., 2002; Evans & Kim, 2013).

Additionally, the living environment also contributes to the risk of STIs. Nainggolan (2024) reported that environments with low supervision increase the risk of sexual violence against children. Meanwhile, Skjælaaen and Vallersnes (2022) found that urban areas with high population density show an increased need for post-sexual violence services. This finding confirms the importance of community and environment-based approaches in prevention and early detection efforts.

Clinical and Policy Implications

Clinically, the results of this study confirm that STI screening in children and adolescents who are victims of sexual violence should be conducted selectively but comprehensively, considering the type of violence, the victim's age, and the timing of the examination. The use of sensitive diagnostic methods, such as PCR-based tests, is becoming increasingly relevant for improving diagnostic accuracy, especially in asymptomatic cases (Tiplamaz & İnanıcı, 2024; Qin & Melvin, 2020). From a policy perspective, these findings support the need to strengthen the integration of health, social, and legal services in addressing sexual violence against children. The implementation of the Sexual Violence Criminal Act and the national guidelines for STIs needs to be accompanied by increased capacity of healthcare workers and a child-friendly referral system (Law No. 12 of 2022; Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia, 2016).

Study Limitations

Although this study provides a comprehensive overview, there are some limitations. Most of the studies reviewed used retrospective or descriptive designs, so causal relationships cannot be definitively concluded. Additionally, the inconsistent variation in diagnostic methods and p-value reporting limits the ability to conduct deeper quantitative comparisons.

CONCLUSION

This literature review indicates that sexually transmitted infections in children and adolescents who are victims of sexual violence are a serious and multidimensional health issue. The occurrence of STIs in this group is influenced by a combination of direct factors, indirect factors, as well as sociodemographic and environmental factors. The findings of this study emphasize the importance of comprehensive and risk-based STI screening for children and adolescents who are victims of sexual violence, taking into account the characteristics of the victims, the type of violence, and the timing of the examination. Strengthening the integration of health, social, and legal services, as well as increasing the capacity of healthcare workers in managing victims of sexual violence, are strategic steps to improve early detection and prevent complications of STIs.

As a literature review, this research is expected to serve as a scientific basis for the development of policies, clinical practices, and further research related to the management of sexually transmitted infections in children and adolescents who are victims of sexual violence, particularly within the context of healthcare and child protection services in Indonesia.

REFERENCES

1. Aaron, K., et al. (2023). Vaginal swab vs urine for detection of *Chlamydia trachomatis*, *Neisseria gonorrhoeae*, and *Trichomonas vaginalis*: A meta-analysis. *Annals of Family Medicine*, 21, 172–179.
2. Abdullahi, A., Nzou, S. M., Kikivi, G., & Mwau, M. (2022). *Neisseria gonorrhoeae* infection in female sex workers in an STI clinic in Nairobi, Kenya. *PLOS ONE*, 17(2), 1–10.
3. Adams, J. A. (2011). Medical evaluation of suspected child sexual abuse: 2011 update. *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse*, 20(5), 588–605.
4. Bambang, A. W., Idrus, I., Amin, S., & Iswanty, M. (2021). Gonorrhea vaginitis in a pediatric patient: A case report. *Pan African Medical Journal*, 38, 1–5.
5. Barberá, M. J., & Serra-Pladevall, J. (2019). Gonococcal infection: An unresolved problem. *Enfermedades Infecciosas y Microbiología Clínica*, 37(7), 458–466.
6. Bjekić, M., Vlajinac, H., Sipetić, S., & Marinković, J. (1997). Risk factors for gonorrhoea: A case-control study. *Genitourinary Medicine*, 73(6), 518–521.
7. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. (2022). Gonococcal infections among neonates. *CDC 24/7*.
8. De Jong, A. R. (1986). Sexually transmitted diseases in sexually abused children. *Sexually Transmitted Diseases*, 13(3), 123–126.
9. De Peder, L. D., et al. (2020). Prevalence of sexually transmitted infections and risk factors among young people in a public health center in Brazil: A cross-sectional study. *Journal of Pediatric and Adolescent Gynecology*, 33(6), 643–650.
10. Dioussé, P., et al. (2020). Sexually transmitted infections among girls aged 1 to 15 years presumed victims of sexual abuse in Thies, Senegal. *Our Dermatology Online*, 11(2), 151–156.
11. Drezett, J., et al. (2020). Sexually transmitted infections among adolescent and adult women victims of sexual violence in the metropolitan region of São Paulo, Brazil. *Human Reproduction Archives*, 36(1), e000320.
12. Driscoll, S. J., et al. (2022). Sexually transmitted infections in suspected child sexual abuse. *Archives of Disease in Childhood*, 108, 53–55.
13. Edwards, J. L., & Butler, E. K. (2011). The pathobiology of *Neisseria gonorrhoeae* lower female genital tract infection. *Frontiers in Microbiology*, 2, 1–11.
14. Chiocca, E. M. (2019). *Advanced pediatric assessment set*. Springer Publishing Company.
15. Evans, G. W., & Kim, P. (2013). Childhood poverty, chronic stress, self-regulation, and coping. *Child Development Perspectives*, 7(1), 43–48.
16. Goodyear-Smith, F., & Schabetsberger, R. (2021). Gonococcus infection probably acquired from bathing in a natural thermal pool: A case report. *Journal of Medical Case Reports*, 15(1), 1–5.
17. Groothuis, J. R., et al. (1983). Pharyngeal gonorrhoea in young children. *Pediatric Infectious Disease*, 2(2), 99–101.
18. Hazra, A., et al. (2022). CDC sexually transmitted infections treatment guidelines, 2021. *JAMA*, 327(9), 870–871.
19. Hornor, G., et al. (2022). Healthcare use and case characteristics of commercial sexual exploitation of children. *Journal of Forensic Nursing*, 19, 160–169.

20. Jang, Y., & Oh, E. (2021). The current status of sexually transmitted infections in South Korean children in the last 10 years. *Osong Public Health and Research Perspectives*, 12, 230–235.
21. Jenny, C., & Crawford-Jakubiak, J. E. (2013). The evaluation of children in the primary care setting when sexual abuse is suspected. *Pediatrics*, 132(2), e558–e567.
22. Kementerian Kesehatan Republik Indonesia. (2016). *Pedoman nasional penanganan infeksi menular seksual*. Kementerian Kesehatan RI.
23. Kementerian Kesehatan Republik Indonesia. (2021). *Pedoman pelayanan dan rujukan kekerasan terhadap perempuan dan anak (KTP/A)*. Direktorat Jenderal Kesehatan Masyarakat.
24. Majeed-Ariss, R., et al. (2021). Utilisation and outcomes of sexually transmitted infection services following child sexual abuse. *Children and Youth Services Review*, 130, 106234.
25. Nainggolan, R. (2024). Identifikasi bakteri diplococcus gram negatif pada sampel swab anal kasus sodomi anak. *Majalah Ilmiah METHODODA*, 14(1), 45–52.
26. Nilasari, H., & Waworuntu, W. (2023). The prevalence of sexually transmitted infections and their association with knowledge, attitudes, and practice in male street children in Indonesia. *International Journal of STD & AIDS*, 35(2), 112–121.
27. Skjælaaen, K., & Vallersnes, O. (2022). Sexually transmitted infections among patients attending a sexual assault centre. *BMJ Open*, 12, e056789.
28. Tao, G., et al. (2023). Sexually transmitted infection/HIV, pregnancy, and mental health-related services provided during visits with sexual assault diagnosis. *Sexually Transmitted Diseases*, 50, 425–431.
29. World Health Organization. (2023). Sexually transmitted infections (STIs). *World Health Organization*.

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